

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF A LITERARY TEXT

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Annotation. When translating a literary text, it is necessary to convey the stylistic features of the original text as fully as possible and preserve its national and cultural flavor. Due to the fact that the pragmatic potential is realized in different languages in different ways, the translator has to resort to different strategies in order to achieve an equivalent communicative effect in the target language. Currently, literary texts are being translated to a large extent, and the need to preserve linguistic and cultural features determines the relevance of the topic articles.

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Linguistic analysis of a literary text is a comprehensive study of a literary and artistic work, with the help of which a system of linguistic means is revealed in it and its ideological, thematic and aesthetic content is transmitted.

The main purpose of linguistic analysis of a literary text is to reveal and realize the initially hidden aspects of a literary work, including the depth of thoughts that the author has stated in the text, and the feelings experienced by the characters. Subject the linguistic analysis of a literary text is directly the linguistic material of the text – it is with him that the researcher will work.

Due to the variety of unique individual characteristics of many authors of works of fiction, linguistic analysis of the text has several options for its implementation. This will allow us to take into account and display the linguistic phenomenon of each writer. Therefore, researchers in each case choose a special way of studying the poetic world of the work. However, modern linguistics has developed some general recommendations for the linguistic analysis of a literary text.

In particular, the successful conduct of this analysis is due to its compliance with the following requirements: the analysis of the text should be oriented from its verbal form to the diverse aspects of its content – figurative-aesthetic, socio-historical, moral, psychological, ideological, etc.; comprehensive consideration of language levels and aspects of the text being studied, all units of which implement artistic and aesthetic function, thereby playing a complementary role; guidance on the principles of consistency and structurality, compliance with which contributes to the identification and understanding of a

set of interrelated and complementary images in the text; definition of those linguistic levels, elements or types of imagery that stylistically prevail in the text and are most significant in the ideological-artistic, style-forming and figurative-aesthetic plans. In addition, some researchers prefer to decompose the linguistic analysis of a literary text into two such major components as literary analysis, that is, the study of a literary work as a historical fact of social development, and stylistic analysis, involving the study of techniques of individual author's use of linguistic means. This is due to the fact that a literary text, first of all, is an organic combination of form and content. The content of linguistic analysis of a literary text For novice researchers, it is recommended to use the general scheme of linguistic text analysis developed on the basis of previously obtained actual results. It is designed in the form of a sequence of the following stages:

- determining the type of speech of the text being studied (narrative, reasoning or description) and its genre features;

- the identification of individual semantic parts and microemes of the text and the establishment of its

 - composition;

- characteristics of the links of the text sentence (the link can be chain, parallel or mixed) and means of their implementation (grammatical and lexical means);

 - definition of the general style of speech in the text and its stylistic features;

- establishing the theme of the text and the means by which its unity is conveyed (syntactic, lexical, morphological and other means of expression);

 - identification of the main idea of the text and formulation of its main idea.

In addition to the sections indicated above, in the process of linguistic analysis of a literary text, the linguistic essence of the following used in the text should be determined language units:

 - obsolete words and phrases;

- outdated or non-normative facts in the field of phonetics, morphology, syntax;

- dialectisms, professionalisms, argotisms and terms unfamiliar to modern man;

 - obsolete and occasional periphrases;

 - incomprehensible facts of poetic symbolism;

- individual author's neologisms in the field of semantics, word formation and compatibility.

Thus, the actions listed above on the characterization and awareness of the designated phenomena and aspects of a work of art constitute the content of its linguistic analysis. Features of linguistic analysis of a literary text The first stage of linguistic analysis is considered to be the skills of slow reading that the researcher has firmly mastered. These skills contribute to the identification of linguistic facts that were used in the literary text, and the explanation of all the variants and meanings of usage, which is one of the most important areas of linguistic analysis.

Linguistic analysis is a complex system that functions to study another system – a work of art. To this end, researchers they resort to the use of various methods and techniques of studying the text, which correspond to the tasks set and the linguistic material of the work. In particular, the research arsenal differs significantly when studying prose and poetic works. The most common methods of linguistic analysis are comparative, structural, functional methods and methods of disciplinary, component, cognitive, discursive analysis. It is also worth emphasizing that linguistic analysis should be conducted at various levels of the language system: phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic, etc.

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